

Documenting Sources of Information in University Theses for Scientific and Humanitarian Disciplines

Khaleda Abd Abdullah, Ali Al-Murtada Abdul Hussein

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 05, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Documentation, bibliographic references, quotes data</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5551230</p>	<p><i>The research aims to know the methods of documenting university theses information sources in the scientific and humanitarian disciplines and the suitability of automated programs for documentation within the Microsoft environment. By testing a number of hypotheses including, the systems for documenting information sources in university theses differ according to the scientific and humanitarian specializations. Refereed scientific journals do not agree in terms of publication conditions to follow a unified system for documenting information sources for research accepted for publication in them. My Microsoft Office systems keep pace in its updates with the documentation systems of global information sources. The research followed the comparative analytical method, included the eye of a 300 degree message, 150 message humanitarian, and 150 scientific message from the search results, The first hypothesis has not been proven. The scientific and humanistic disciplines have agreed to use the system APA And a rate of 74.6% in scientific disciplines, and 36.6% in humanitarian disciplines. Proving the second hypothesis, as the publication conditions varied in the use of the documentation system in scientific journals. Proving the third hypothesis, as updates continue to the documentation systems of information sources in Microsoft versions. The research presents a number of suggestions including, unifying the conditions for publication in scientific journals. The information and library specialists review the versions of Microsoft systems, and propose amendments that comply with the rules of the bibliographic description.</i></p>

Introduction

Scientific research remains the basis for the development of science and the progress of societies, and it is difficult to complete an integrated scientific research without an adequate balance of sources of information that can be relied upon and used, reading, analyzing and understanding in order to reach the results.

These sources are the basis for scientific research, and from this point it was necessary for researchers to document the sources that are relied upon in their research and refer to them to give them the degree of impact, as well as their indications of access to reliable and modern scientific studies, and their extent and reading to shed light on the multiple aspects of the subject. The study and the researchers who contributed to the study and the statement of their participation, as well as the preservation of a number of scientific research ethics, such as the scientific secretariat and intellectual property. It is noted the diversity of documentation methods in university theses, both in the scientific disciplines and in the humanities and social disciplines.

This research attempts to investigate the most well-known and followed documentation systems in writing the approved sources of information in university theses, how to refer to them, their places in the body or footnote, or in the list of references, and the most internationally accredited in writing university theses or research in scientific journals, approved in Microsoft publications. Office, and an explanation of how to document a number of systems for documenting information sources, including

Modern Languages Association System
Harvard system
Chicago system
American Psychological Association system
Mendelian system

Method

Follow in explaining how to document, and the required data fields, and clarifying them in a way that helps the researcher understand them and enables him to choose the most appropriate way to organize his research sources.

The practical part was on five systems
Documenting information sources with a system MLA:1-

<p>Author's name . Title in italics , edition statements, statements of responsibility as the corrected translator, city : publisher , year . Pages Such as : Kandilji , Amer Ibrahim . <i>Documentation</i> , Cairo :The Egyptian General Authority for Authoring and Publishing , 2008 .44 p</p>	book
<p>Author's name " . Title ," Statement of Liability , City: Publisher , Year . Pages Ex : Gharib Ahmed " . Goodness and Evil ," Baghdad : House of Wisdom , 2008 .24 p</p>	chapter of a book
<p>author . Title , Edition , E-book , Statement of Liability , City: Publisher , Year . pages . Link Such as : Al -Zaidi , Samer . <i>General psychology</i> . I 2,e-book , Baghdad:Dar Al Hur , 2012 http://marsal.com</p>	Electronic Book
<p>Book name . Surah / Chapter Name : Verse No such as: Holy Quran . Star : 4-4</p>	Holy book
<p>The last name, then the first name of the narrator . Book title . investigation . edition . the part . Country : publishing house, year of publication</p>	Quotes by the Prophet
<p>Author's name . Address in italics . Investigation / translation. Edition , part , place of publication : publishing house, year of publication such as: Al-Jawhari, Abu Nasr Ismail bin Hammad . <i>The crown of the language and the Arabic sahih</i> . investigation . Ahmed Abdel Ghafour Attar . I 4 ,c 4 ,Beirut : Dar Al Ilm ,2009</p>	Dictionaries, dictionaries and scientific encyclopedias

Documenting information sources in the Chicago system:

book	<p>in the footnote First and last name ,book title , investigation / translation/ compilation . edition) . Country : Publishing House, Publication Year , (Part : Page No Such as Amer Ibrahim Kandilji, <i>Scientific Research and the Use of Traditional and Electronic Information Sources</i>) Cairo : Dar Al-Hikma, undated ,(p383 .</p> <p>Ahmed Shibli ,<i>how to write a research or a letter</i> . 24 Edition) Cairo : The Egyptian Renaissance Library ,1997(in references The last name and then the first name of the author . Book title .Investigation / translation / compilation . edition . the part . Country : publishing house, year of publication Such as Kandelji, Amer Ibrahim . Scientific research and the use of traditional and electronic information sources) . Cairo : House of Wisdom, undated (p .383 Shibli, Ahmed . How to write a search or a letter . 24 Edition) Cairo : The Egyptian Renaissance Library ,1997(</p>
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Holy book	<p>In the reference list Book name . Surah / Chapter Name : Verse No For example : the Holy Quran . Star : 4-5</p> <p>in the footnote Book name , Surah / chapter name : Verse number Such as : the Noble Qur'an , the star : 4-5</p>
Electronic Book	<p>Author's name . Title , edition data , e-book) country : publisher, year .(Then the link, if any Same in footnotes and reference list Such as Zaidi , Samer . <i>General psychology . i ,2 e-book</i> Baghdad:Freedom House , 2011(http://marsal.com</p>
Dictionaries, dictionaries and scientific encyclopedias	<p>in the footnote First and last name of the author, title, investigation / translation, translation, edition) . Country : Publishing House, Publication Year , (Part : Article Such as Abu Nasr Ismail bin Hammad Al-Gohary ,<i>Taj Al-Lughah and Sahih Al-Arabiya</i> , p . Ahmed Abdel Ghafour Attar ,4edition) Beirut : Dar Al-Ilm for Millions ,2009 , (Part :4 Article ” WQ“</p> <p>In the reference list The last name and then the first name of the author . address. Investigation / translation . edition . the part . Country : publishing house, year of publication Such as Al-Jawhari, Abu Nasr Ismail bin Hammad . The crown of the language and the Arabic sahih . The Open . Ahmed Abdel Ghafour Attar . Edition 4 .Part 4 .)Beirut : House of Science for Millions ,2009(</p>
website	<p>Author's name . Post title , page name , link . date of viewing Example Mohamed , Ahmed . Dictionary of meanings see : http://www.almaany.com/ar/dict/ar-ar/ Accessed : December 12, 2015</p>
Manuscripts	<p>in the margin First and last name of the author ,<i>title of manuscript</i> , date of copy, name of collection, deposit number, place of deposit, country, chapter title. Such as : Muhammad IbnYunus Al-Senussi, A Nice Brief on Logic,895 A.H., An-Najah National University Library, Nablus, Introduction</p> <p>in references Last name, first name . The title of the manuscript . copy date. Group name . Deposit number . place of deposit . country . Chapter title. Such as : Al-Senussi, Muhammad bin Yunus . Nice brief in logic. 895AH</p>

Documenting information sources in the Harvard system:

book	<p>Author's name) year ,(title . Edition , place of publication : then publisher , pages Such as Omar, Ahmed) 2008 ,(History of Arabic Language , Cairo : Egyptian General Authority for authoring and publishing , p . 44</p>
Holy book	So what is the name of the book . Surah / Chapter Name: Verse No

	Such as Holy Quran . Star : 4-5
Electronic Book	Author's name) year ,(title . Edition , place of publication : the publisher , the place where the book or series was taken ,then in square brackets, it is written online if it was taken online, or an e-book if it was taken from another place . Then the link, if any Such as : Al -Ghanim , Salah Ali) 2013 (Children's Violent Behavior : The Role of the Family and Society . Floor 2 ,Cairo , Cairo University . Electronic book library]online[.Available at the link the https : //www.book.com/book2349
Research in a scientific journal	Author's name , title Search in quotation marks with one superscript , ' name of the journal , monthly, yearly or daily if any, volume . Number and number , then year and month , then r and page numbers Such as : Al - Naimi , good God good ' scientific research between modernity and originality , 'Journal of the builders of generations, monthly volume 19 ,number 74 , 2010 0May , pp . 84-109
Article in a local magazine	The same method as the first and add the day with the month and year
articleonline	The same method as the first, and at the end the website link is added with writing the time of the visit in the day, month, year, hour and minute Al-Nuaimi , Khairallah Hassan ” ,Scientific Research between Modernity and Authenticity “ ,Builders of Generations Magazine, Monthly Volume 19 ,Issue 74 , 2010 ,May , pp .84-109 .Available link http://www.hurras.org/vb/showthread.php
website	Author's name , publication title , page name , link . date of viewing Example Muhammad , Ahmed , the dictionary of meanings see : http://www.almaany.com/ar/dict/ar-ar/ Accessed : December 12, 2015

Documenting information sources in the Vancouver system:

book	Steedman's medical dictionary. 26th ed. Baltimore: Williams & Wilkins; 1995. Apraxia; p.119-20.
Electronic Book	Steedman's medical dictionary. *Internet+. 26th ed. Baltimore: Williams & Wilkins; 1995. Apraxia; p.119-20. [cited 2009 Nov 11].Available from: http://www.stedmans.com
Magazine article	Snowdon J. Severe depression at old age. Medicine Today. 2002 Dec;3(12):40-47.
Article in an online magazine	Lemanek K. Adherence issues in the medical management of asthma. J PediatrPsychol [Internet]. 1990 [cited 2010 Apr 22];15(4):437-58. Available from: http://jpepsy.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/reprint/15/4/437
website	Drivers told: "Don't use Clem7 tunnel". The Courier Mail [Internet].2010 Mar 16 [cited 2010 Mar 16]; Available from: http://www.couriermail.com.au/news/car-with-flat-tyre-the-first-to-cause-problems-in-clem7-tunnel/story-e6freon6-1225841179464

Documentation according to the system APA:

The application needs a system APA Experience and practice in using Microsoft Word after opening the Word program interface in the program and after writing the required text, followed by the process of documenting text sources

The system process is as follows
First: Go to reference list

From this list, an icon for references and quotes appears

Then go to choose the pattern and among the available patterns is a pattern APA

Then go with the ruler on the citation required to be documented and then to insert a citation and choose to add a new source

the first field It is a field for the author in which the author is written. But if the author is an institution, there is a box below this field. When you click on it, the field will turn down automatically and the name of the institution is written

the author's writing, there is a rectangle to the left of the author's field with the word Edit when you click on it, a list of fields for the author appears.

The sum of scientific theses
150

Other	Chicago	Harvard	MLA	APA	Vancouver
8	zero	5	zero	112	25
				medicine	Specialization
				9	the number

Vancouver	the system
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Educational psychology and teaching methods	Specialization
10	the number
APA	the system

computer Sciences	Specialization
21	the number
APA	the system
Chemistry Science	Specialization
10	the number
APA	the system

Veterinary medicine		Specialization	
2	4	4	the number
Harvard	APA	Vancouver	the system

mathematics	Specialization
10	the number
APA	the system
Physics Science	Specialization
10	the number
APA	the system

Farming	Specialization	
10	the number	
APA	the system	
engineering	Specialization	
21	the number	
APA	the system	
Life sciences	Specialization	
10	the number	
APA	the system	
Physical Education		Specialization
2	8	the number
APA	footnote	the system

Human messages
Number of messages
150

Vancouver	APA	MLA	Chicago	Harvard	Other
zero	55	29	48	48	10
				geographical	Specialization
				10	the number
				APA	the system
				Political Science	Specialization
				2	8 the number
				APA	MLA the system

information and libraries		Specialization	
2	4	4	the number
Harvard	MLA	APA	the system

Law	Specialization	
3	7	the number
APA	MLA	the system

Arabic language literature	Specialization
10	the number
Chicago	the system

media	Specialization	
2	8	the number
APA	Chicago	the system

Specialization	psychology
the number	10
the system	APA

Arabic language education	Specialization
10	the number
Chicago	the system
etiquette history	Specialization
10	the number
Chicago	the system
Quran sciences and Islamic education	Specialization
10	the number
footnote	the system

Philosophy	Specialization
10	the number
APA	the system
breeding history	Specialization
10	the number
Chicago	the system
Administration and Economics	Specialization
10	the number
APA	the system

Fine Arts	Specialization
10	the number
MLA	the system

Sociology	Specialization	
4	6	the number
APA	Harvard	the system

Comparing documentation according to scientific and human documentation

Scientific	the system
112	APA
zero	MLA
5	Harvard
zero	Vancouver
25	other
8	

APA	55	36.66%
MLA	29	19.3%
Vancouver	zero	0%
Chicago	48	36%
Harvard	8	5.33%
other	10	6.6%

human messages

most used APA by 67.4% with a slight difference from Chicago 36% and less used Harvard by 3.3% and not using Vancouver 0%
scientific messages

6,74%	112	APA
6,16%	25	Vancouver
36%	zero	Chicago
3,3%	zero	MLA
3,3%	5	Harvard
3,5%	8	other

that more used APA by 74% and the least used Harvard by 3.3% did not use Harvard and MLA 0%

Comparison and analysis between the humanitarian and scientific specialization

the number	the system
167	APA
29	MLA
13	Harvard
25	Vancouver
48	Chicago
18	other

It is clear through analysis and comparison that there is a big difference in use, where the system outperforms APA. Nearest competitor is Chicago, with 39%.

It is found by looking at all the messages that have been selected

There is no message from the messages I used a system other than APA Completely and according to the published guide correctly

Where it turned out that all the letters that used the Chicago, Harvard and . system MLA Documentation was not used in the text and was satisfied with digital documentation of the text

Most of the documentation is used in the footnote, and the systems we mentioned are not used in the footnote, with the exception of Chicago. If the footnote is used, it has special rules, and documentation is not used in references.

Result and discussion

After analyzing the data and comparing the use of information source documentation systems in university theses in scientific and humanitarian disciplines, the research resulted in a number of results, including

There was no fixed system, whether in the scientific disciplines, or the humanities in documenting sources. Some disciplines are unique in using a specific system, for example, the use of a system APA in university theses in psychology, philosophy and educational topics. As for the Arabic language subjects, the Chicago system was used, and the Vancouver system was used in medical subjects. The most used system is the system APA, where the number of messages reached 167 message out of 300 in all disciplines grew by 55.5% of the total messages. The most widely used system in scientific disciplines is the . system APA with 122 messages out of 150, with a rate of 74.6%. The system most commonly used in the humanities is the . system APA. It was used in documenting sources for 55 messages, at a rate of 36.6%, a difference of 7 letters from Chicago, and the least used system is Harvard, with only 8 letters, at a rate of 5.33%. The Vancouver system was not used in documenting the sources of any university thesis in the humanities specialties of the study sample. Poor compliance with the requirements of documentation systems in the text, and in the list of references correctly in the study sample theses. The most commonly used system in university theses, the research sample is the system APA

Conclusions

Researchers and authors in documentation face the problem of unifying the entries to document the Arabic names in the text and the list of references. Surname, and in the list of references in the first name.

In this case, the researchers resort to preparing the list of sources manually when entering the author field and by clicking on the word edit on the left, three fields will appear : the first with the last name, the second with the first name, and the third with the middle name, so it is written manually by flipping the title and following it with a comma, then completing the writing The name in the family field, this is what will make the name appear uniformly in the body and in the list of references.

But when filling these fields with information only and writing them as proven by the order in the fields that appear in the system window, then the entries will appear not unified, in addition to writing them in the same way in the sequence that appears in the window, i.e., the first name field, or the second name field, it will appear Distractedly too.

And when you type it in this way in the author field directly without pressing Edit, the first source will appear with the title only, and the second source will show the whole name and form upside down, but with the title.

The best way is to write the full name in the family field and flip it manually with a comma after the name.To solve the problem of documentation by name as a main entry in the text is long and intended for the title exclusively, and there is another way to solve this matter, which is to click on the source in the text and go to the arrow at the bottom left of the source and choose to convert the source to a fixed text, then the rest of the name can be deleted from the text and the complete source documentation will appear in the reference list.

system features APA With the ability to quickly prepare a list of references, by clicking on the references and citations option in the toolbar, one click will show all the sources that have been proven and documented.

Another problem that researchers face is editing and arranging the list of references APA Arrange them according to their occurrence in the research, whether they are in Arabic, or in other languages, and this is what some researchers do not want, where the alphabetical arrangement is optimal, or separating the sources in Arabic from the sources in foreign languages.

This problem can be solved in this system as well, by following the following:

After completing a list of references, go to the references, options will appear, including updating references, and this option can be placed any new source that was not initially documented and added. After completing the list of references, you can click here on Update References and it will appear in the list

Next to the option to update references, there are three vertical dots and a small down arrow with a file shape in the middle. When you click on it, the reference selection patterns will appear. At the bottom, there are two options, the first is to convert references to static text, and when you convert them to static text, you can copy and delete the list and then paste what has been copied to enable In this way, edit the list and arrange it alphabetically

The second choice from this list is to choose the language. When you click on this option and choose the language, it will appear with its language sources only.

In this way, it is possible to separate Arabic and foreign sources and arrange them alphabetically

By clicking documented in the text, three vertical dots will appear on the right and an arrow down the left. When you click on the arrow, several options will appear, the first of which is to edit the quote, and this allows adding pages or the option to prevent the author, title or year from appearing when clicking on any circle, and the second option is to edit the source This makes it possible to completely modify the source and in any field without referring to the list of inserting a citation. The third option is to convert the citation into a fixed text, and when it is converted, it cannot be modified again and it will be exactly the same as the text .

Features APA It is also to keep the sources documented by the system and by clicking on any documented source with one click, all fields will be filled directly without returning to it again.

Documenting the different forms of information sources includes all by choosing the type of source at the top right of the window, and if it is not available, it is possible to choose a variety.

In choosing the sources management, the sources that have been documented in the various researches are all located on the file in the computer. You can click on the sources management and then choose Delete, which will delete all the sources, or choose copies that copy all the sources, and choose Edit to make modifications to writing the sources or taking a specific source.

What distinguishes this system is the placement of information in the required fields, and the system will take care of placing the bibliographic signs, and this is what the researcher was suffering from a lot.

The global trend and international journals towards documentation with the . systemAPA Quickly for ease of development, periodically and continuously, and keeping pace with developments in scientific quality standards for publication in journals and containers.

The possibility of using it in scientific and human subjects alike due to its flexibility and the possibility of adding, deleting and modifyingThe possibility of linking Microsoft to one of the automated programs for free citations, such as the Mend Elian system, this will allow the authentication automatically without filling in the

fields in the system APA By taking the text quoted from the source and clicking on the program icon, it will automatically document whether the source is saved on the computer or quoted from the Internet

Recommendations

Attention to documenting sources is like paying attention to the content of the message because it is no less important than the content of the message. Apply the conditions of publication in scientific journals and know the documentation required then and use it to ensure the authenticity of the documentation of the sources and the possibility of publishing in refereed journals .On disciplines that did not use the system APAReconsider the use of the system. Because it is accredited in documenting sources in international journals. Keeping abreast of developments related to documentation systems in Microsoft Word programs, as it helps in addressing gaps, and provides what the researcher needs in documentationInformation and librarians review the versions of Microsoft systems, and suggest appropriate modifications according to the rules of bibliographic description, especially with regard to writing resources in the Arabic language.

Notes Acknowledgment or notes

He drew the attention of scientific departments in faculties to the interest in teaching documentation systems and including them in school curricula, especially in the subject of scientific research curricula for primary and higher studies.Shedding light on the documentation systems in Microsoft Word versions and how to master them in preparing university theses.

Conducting subsequent studies for this study concerned with evaluating one or more documentation systems in Microsoft Word versions and proposing appropriate modifications to be compatible with writing Arabic names as an entry point for documentation and circulating the results to scientific departments to control documentation systems and prepare a list of references.

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Author Information

Khaleda Abdullah

Al-Mustansiriya University

Ali Al-Murtada Abdul Hussein

Al-Mustansiriya University
